

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF Al-Zn-Mg/SiC_p COMPOSITES AT AMBIENT AND ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

N.V.Ravi Kumar and E.S.Dwarakadasa
Department of Metallurgy
Indian Institute of Science
Bangalore 560 012, INDIA.

ABSTRACT

Among the aluminium alloys, the 7xxx series (Al-Zn-Mg) alloys develop the highest strength but SiC_p reinforcement in this system does not seem to improve the properties. The reasons can be traced to the lack of effective load transfer to the particles and to the strain localisation in the matrix which is influenced by the matrix microstructure. The particle/matrix interface also plays a crucial role. As a part of this study, mechanical properties in tension and compression were evaluated and discussed for Al-Zn-Mg/SiC_p composites with different volume fractions of SiC_p after various thermal aging conditions both at room and elevated temperatures.

INTRODUCTION

The discontinuously reinforced aluminium (DRA) materials with SiC_p are receiving increasing attention for applications in automobile, aircraft, aerospace and other engineering sectors because of their high specific stiffness, wear resistance, elevated temperature strength compared to monolithic materials[1,2]. Various commercial alloys in the 2000, 6000 and 7000 series have been studied to understand the underlying mechanisms of deformation and fracture[3,4]. Broadly the processing method and other thermomechanical treatments such as homogenisation, extrusion and heat treatment control the matrix microstructure, particle distribution and the interface.

Al-Zn-Mg alloys dispersed with SiC_p particles do not seem to improve the strength[5,6]. Lewandowski and co-workers have studied the effect of microstructure on fracture and fracture toughness[7-9]; a decrease in yield strength is often reported with additions of SiC_p and, generally, studies were limited to powder metallurgy processed composites. Considering the sensitivity of this alloy to the heat treatment and the good dependence of the mechanical properties on the microstructure[10], it was felt necessary to carry out systematic investigations on the effect of microstructure on the tensile and compressive behaviour on this system of composites. Accordingly, certain observations made on cast and extruded Al-Zn-Mg/SiC_p composites are reported in this paper.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

DTD 5024 (Al-Zn-Mg) alloys and SiC particles of 40 μm average size were utilised to prepare 0,9 and 18% composites by stir casting technique, the details of which are given elsewhere[11]. The composition of the base material is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Chemical composition of the control alloy

Zn	Mg	Cu	Mn	Fe	Si	Al
5.3	2.8	0.5	0.48	0.2	0.3	Bal.

The SiC_p distribution shown in Fig.1 indicates a broad size range. The particles, shown in the same figure, are irregular, angular and are have sharp corners.

Figure 1. SiC particle distribution along with their irregular shapes and sharp corners

The cast billets were given a homogenising treatment at 485°C for 24h, furnace cooled and hot extruded at a temperature of 480°C with an extrusion ratio of 16:1. Room temperature uniaxial tension and compression test were carried out in accordance with ASTM E8 and E9 in an Instron model 8032 with constant cross head speed of 4mm/min. The samples were solutionised at 485°C for 1.5h and quenched in cold water (25°C) and different tempers were given. High temperature tensile tests were carried out at a constant cross head speed of 1.5 mm/min. after T6 treatment.

RESULTS

Microstructure

Particle distribution in the 9 and 18% extruded composites are shown in Fig.2. Particle distribution is uniform, but regions which are relatively particle free along with agglomerates can be seen in 9% composite. As a whole in both cases most of the particles are well separated and the distribution is nonuniform only on a microscopic scale. Fine particles, which are below the range shown in Fig.1, can be seen in the background which indicates that some particle breakage occurred during processing of these composites.

Figure 2. Distribution of SiC in (a) 9% (b) 18%

Mechanical properties

Room temperature mechanical properties, in different tempers, are given in Table 2. In both tension and compression, 0.2% offset yield strength was determined though it is known that composites exhibit rapid work hardening rate in the initial strains. In the case of tension, in T4 condition composites exhibited higher yield strength levels than the control alloy. But in the other two conditions (i.e., T6 and T7 tempers) the yield stress values showed a decreasing trend. The UTS values are also lower in the case of composites, but there is a significant fall in the case of T6 temper. In all the cases, a drop in ductilities is observed with volume fraction having insignificant influence.

In compression, except for the peak aged condition, yield stress values were found to be either equal or exhibited an improvement over that of the monolithic material. Even in T6 condition, the decrease is not as drastic as it was found to be in tension.

The fracture surfaces of 18% composite are shown in Fig.3. In the peak aged condition, fractographic examinations of tensile fractures exhibited particle fracture and interface debonding. Significant matrix deformation is evident. In the other two conditions also (i.e., T4 and T7 conditions) the fracture surfaces of 18% composite showed similar features except that the matrix exhibited more deformation around the particles with ductile tearing.

Table 2. Room temperature property data (MPa) in tension and compression

Material (% SiC)	Temper	Tension			Compression
		0.2%YS	UTS	%el	0.2%YS
0	As solutionised(T4)	145	320	22.0	140
9		164	298	17.4	170
18		177	248	8.1	208
0	135/16h(T6)	533	561	11.7	510
9		453	492	2.7	513
18		420	420	1.7	495
0	135/16h+170/36h(T7)	418	495	15.2	394
9		397	408	4.3	390
18		360	367	1.9	433

Figure 3. Fracture surfaces of 18% composite tested in tension in (a) T4 (b) T6 and (c) T7 conditions

Longitudinal sections of the fractured samples observed under SEM indicated various levels of damage in different tempers(Fig.4). In T4 condition, particle fracture along with the interface decohesion in many locations were seen. In contrast the peak aged temper did not exhibit any damage indicating that the deformation is highly localised. The composite with T7

temper also did not show any specific features. However, cracks in the matrix were observed at some locations.

High temperature test data given in Fig.5 shows a decrease in 9% composite yield strength compared to the base alloy but the rate of decrease is more for control alloy than for the composite and ultimately there seems to be a cross over at higher temperatures. The percentage RA values increases rapidly for the base alloy than for the composite. For the composite, only after 300°C, there is marginal increase in reduction in area.

Figure 4. Longitudinal sections of the tensile specimens for 18% composite in (a) T4 (b) T6 (c) & (d) T7 conditions. The damage in the matrix is shown by arrows for T7 condition

Figure 5. Effect of temperature on the yield strength and % RA of the control alloy and 9% composite tested in tension

DISCUSSION

The decrease in the yield strength values in the case of Al-Zn- Mg/SiC_p composites have not been properly understood. According to Humphreys[5], the stresses on the brittle reinforcement can be large when composites with high strength matrixes are strained. Consequently, depending on the interfacial strength, particle fracture can occur or before the loads get transferred interface can give way. Once either of these things happen during elastic loading, the net load carrying capacity of the composite decreases and thus yield stress might decrease. Davies et al.[12] advocated two competing mechanisms such as the load transfer and the inhibition of plastic relaxation at the interface for strengthening in this system of composites. According to Hunt et al.[13] two important parameters that control the void nucleation process are the matrix yield strength and the work hardening behaviour. The primary role of increasing yield strength is to activate a greater number of potential nucleation sites by making more particle/matrix interfaces to reach their decohesion stress or by increasing the frequency of particle cracking.

In a practical situation, void nucleation can occur preferentially in the regions of microstructure which exhibit the largest local volume fraction of particles due to increased stress concentrations at the interfaces in these areas.

The decrease of tensile yield stress and UTS with particle loading in case of peak aged and overaged conditions can be due to the rapid nucleation of the voids at the interface and at the particles and the associated propagation of crack through the clustered regions. The absence of any damage in the peak aged condition just below the fracture surface indicates that the stresses are highly localised. But again, evidence of particle cracking along with interfacial separation in T4 condition indicates the uniform deformation over considerable lengths and the weakness of the interface. The ductile tearing around the debonded particles(Fig. 3a) indicates that the separation of the interface might have taken place in the later stages of deformation, which resulted in the decrease in UTS values. Though the processing routes are different, Davies et al.[12] also observed interfacial decohesion in their P/M composites and at present the reasons for this are unknown. Efforts are on to trace this with the processing route and the thermal treatments that were given. As for the overaged temper, in literature, a preference for the interfacial failure and matrix damage has been observed[8,14] for MB78 (Al-7Zn-2Mg-2Cu-0.14Zr) with SiC_p. But in the present work with similar heat treatment this was not observed frequently. The difference in processing and the matrix composition might be reasons for this. But the lesser number of particles on the fracture surface compared to their counterparts in other tempers do indicate a preference of the crack to avoid the particles as a whole.

As for the temperature effect, the lesser rate of decrease in the yield strength in the 9% composite again indicates the gradual decrease in strain localisation and the possible role of the interface in the load transfer process. However, further work is necessary at various strain rates to elucidate the relaxation mechanisms that are operative. The % RA values indicate that the composite is fairly resistant to necking.

Compression testing under similar conditions of matrix microstructure is not much sensitive to local particle distribution and the associated damage. Hence it can provide a better rationale for comparison. In the light of that, the present observations may be explained through the above arguments. Depending on the matrix microstructure, the load transfer to the particles and the associated strain localisation operate in mutually opposite ways. Wherever the strain is not getting distributed, it is expected to generate certain damage in the material which can give rise to lower values of yield stress. Consequently, in T6 temper, the identical values

for 0 and 9% composite compared to the 18% material which showed the lesser yield strength may be due to the domination of damage due the strain localisation. In the T7 condition, the opposite effect could be seen which is manifested in the increase in yield strength with SiC_p content.

In the end, there are a couple of points to be noted. Firstly, the general lack of interface cohesion might have as well influenced the mechanical behaviour, specifically in compression. Yet, that does not fully explain the observed trends in the present work. Secondly, how the strain localisation gets manifested with all the microstructural features of a composite processed typically with solidification route is to be addressed in detail through further work.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The observed trend in the yield strength values for the base alloy and composites in compression may be due to the effect of matrix microstructure on the load transfer and the strain localisation. In tension, in addition to that, various levels of damage accumulation was observed depending on the microstructure.

REFERENCES

1. D.L.McDANELS, NASA Technical Paper 2302, July 1984
2. S.V.NAIR, J.K.TIEN and R.C.BATES, *Int.Met.Rev.* **30** (1985) 275
3. JODY N.HALL, J.WAYNE JONES and ANIL K.SACHDEV, *Mat.Sci.Engg.*, **A183** (1994) 69
4. J.W.LUSTER, M.THUMANN and R.BAUMANN, *Mat.Sci.Tech.*, **9** (1993) 853
5. F.J.HUMPHREYS in *Mechanical and Physical Behaviour of Metallic and Ceramic Composites* (edited by S.I.Anderson et al.) Riso Natn.Lab., Denmark (1988) 51
6. T.J.A.GOEL, M.H.LORETTO and P.BOWEN, *Composites* **24** (1993) 270
7. J.J.LEWANDOWSKI, C.LIU and W.H.HUNT Jr., in *Processing and Properties for Powder Metallurgy Composites* (eds. P.Kumar, K.Vedula and A.Ritter), TMS-AIME, Warrendale, Pa (1987) 117.
8. J.J.LEWANDOWSKI, C.LIU and W.H.HUNT Jr., *Mater.Sci.Engg* **A107**, (1989) 241
9. M.MANOHARAN and J.J.LEWANDOWSKI, *Acta metall.mater.* **38** (1990) 489
10. S.I.HONG, G.T.GREY III and J.J.LEWANDOWSKI, *Acta metall.mater.* **41** (1993) 2337
11. N.V.RAVI KUMAR and E.S.DWARAKADASA, *J.Mater.Sci.* **29** (1994) 1533
12. C.H.J.DAVIES, N.RAGHUNATHAN and T.SHEPPARD, *Mat.Sci.Tech.* **8** (1992) 977
13. W.H.HUNT Jr., O.RICHMAND and R.D.YOUNG in *Proceedings of the sixth international conference on composite materials, Vol.2* (Eds.F.L.Matthews et al.) 2.189; 1987, Amsterdam/London, Elsevier Applied Science.
14. PREET M.SINGH and JOHN J.LEWANDOWSKI, *Metall.Trans.* **24A** (1993) 2531

BEHAVIOUR OF HIGH TEMPERATURE MATRIX SYSTEMS
